

The Effect of Entrepreneurship Education on The Determinants of Entrepreneurial Intention Among Higher Education Students

L'impact de l'éducation entrepreneuriale sur les déterminants de l'intention entrepreneuriale chez les étudiants de l'enseignement supérieur

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ABSTRACT :

This article investigates the effect of entrepreneurship education on the determinants of entrepreneurial intention among higher education students. Using a deductive method at a descriptive level, based on data from articles in the Scopus database, focusing on publications from 2018 to 2024 to provide an up-to-date insight. The findings reveal that entrepreneurship education significantly influences the determinants of entrepreneurial intention. This research highlights the value of entrepreneurship education in fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among higher education students, providing insights for educators, policymakers, and researchers.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial education, determinants of entrepreneurial intention, higher education students.

RÉSUMÉ :

Cet article étudie l'effet de l'éducation entrepreneuriale sur les déterminants de l'intention entrepreneuriale chez les étudiants de l'enseignement supérieur. En utilisant une méthode déductive à un niveau descriptif, basée sur des données d'articles dans la base de données Scopus, en se concentrant sur les publications de 2018 à 2024 pour fournir un aperçu actualisé. Les résultats révèlent que l'éducation entrepreneuriale influence de manière significative les déterminants de l'intention entrepreneuriale. Cette recherche met en évidence la valeur de l'enseignement de l'entrepreneuriat dans la promotion d'un état d'esprit entrepreneurial chez les étudiants de l'enseignement supérieur, fournissant des informations aux éducateurs, aux décideurs politiques et aux chercheurs.

Mots-clés: L'éducation entrepreneuriale, déterminants de l'intention entrepreneurial, étudiants de l'enseignement supérieur.

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship, a concept first defined in literature over two centuries ago (Mudalige, 2022), has evolved to become a cornerstone of economic growth and innovation in today's global economy. While definitions vary, entrepreneurship is commonly defined as “an individual's ability to transform ideas into viable new ventures” (Adeel et al., 2023), encompassing dimensions such as risk-taking, opportunity capture, and change orientation. Stevenson and Jarillo-Mossi (1986) aptly described it as "a process of creating value by bringing together a unique package of resources to exploit an opportunity."

In recent years, cultivating entrepreneurial intention, particularly among youth and higher education students, has gained significant attention from researchers, policymakers, and educators alike. This focus is driven by recognizing entrepreneurship as a key driver of economic growth and sustainable community development (Badri & Hachicha, 2019; De Vita et al., 2014). As global economies continue to evolve, fostering entrepreneurial mindsets and skills has increasingly become crucial for both individual success and societal progress.

Entrepreneurship education has emerged as a vital tool in this endeavor, by offering pedagogical programs and processes designed to nurture entrepreneurial attitudes and skills (Fayolle et al., 2006). Universities, in particular, have been identified as pivotal institutions in fostering youth entrepreneurship through specialized programs and experiential learning opportunities (Aga, 2023). The integration of entrepreneurship education across various disciplines is advocated to empower students from diverse academic backgrounds to pursue entrepreneurial ventures (Pacheco & Franco, 2023).

This research seeks to explore the influence of entrepreneurship education on the determinants of entrepreneurial behavior among higher education students. Students represent the ideal population for examining entrepreneurial intention because they encounter career decisions upon graduation (Krueger, 2000). By examining the nuanced interplay between education, and the determinants of entrepreneurial intention, we aim to contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors shaping the entrepreneurial landscape. To this end, the study addresses the following main research question: To what extent does entrepreneurship education impact the determinants of entrepreneurial intention among higher education students?

In the following sections, we will present the methodology guiding our study and delve into the existing literature to establish the theoretical framework employed to explore these intersections.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research employs a systematic approach using a deductive method conducted at a descriptive level using documentary analysis. This methodological choice allows for a structured examination of existing literature to draw specific conclusions about our topic.

To identify relevant studies, the Scopus database served as the primary source. The search focused on publications from 2018 to 2024 to ensure the inclusion of recent trends and developments, providing up-to-

date insights and recommendations. This period is substantial enough to observe patterns and changes over time.

Content analysis was employed to interpret the data, allowing for the identification of key themes and patterns across the selected studies. This qualitative analysis technique helps in understanding the nuanced aspects of entrepreneurship education and intention.

The search was limited to articles written in English to maintain consistency and ensure the accessibility of the analyzed studies. The search terms and number of bibliographic references reviewed are summarized as follows :

Table 1: Bibliographic search terms

Entrepreneurship education	15,502
Entrepreneurial intention	5,194
Entrepreneurship education and determinants of entrepreneurial intention	133

Source: Own elaboration

Based on this, we proceeded to include the papers that are relevant to our research.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1. Entrepreneurship education :

3.1.1. History and development of entrepreneurial education :

The history of entrepreneurship education dates back to the establishment of the subject for the first time at Harvard University in 1947, with widespread adoption across educational systems globally by the 2000s (Katz, 2003; Neck & Corbett, 2018). In many countries worldwide enterprise education keeps rising to the top of the political agenda (Anderson & Jack, 2008). Over the past years, entrepreneurship education has grown dramatically in colleges and universities across the globe. As the number of university courses in entrepreneurship continues to grow, so does the number of students. A 2006 study found that over 400,000 students annually take 2,200 courses at 1,600 schools nationwide (Finkle et al., 2006).

This historical context highlights the evolving expectations placed on universities to contribute to socioeconomic development (Morawska-Jancelewicz, 2022). Responding to these expectations, many universities have embraced entrepreneurship as a means of fostering community development and supporting entrepreneurial activities among faculty and students (Pereira & Franco, 2023). This has led to the rise of the entrepreneurial university paradigm, where institutions promote entrepreneurship through various means such as education, incubation and acceleration of new ventures, knowledge commercialization, and collaboration with government and industry (Soetanto & Van Geenhuizen, 2019).

Entrepreneurship education (EE) emerges as a first step to gaining employment for young people and contributing to economic growth (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2018; Newman et al., 2019). Entrepreneurship education is essential for equipping the next generation with the skills needed to

address global challenges (Winkler, 2024). According to the European Commission (2017), EE equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to succeed in today's dynamic market.

Education systems worldwide have strategically embraced entrepreneurship education to enhance employment outcomes for young people (Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education, 2018). Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (2018) suggests that integrating entrepreneurship education into curricula can enhance students' employability and equip them with the entrepreneurial mindset needed to navigate an increasingly competitive job market. Not only for Business students, the integration of entrepreneurship education across disciplines is advocated to empower students from diverse academic backgrounds (Pacheco & Franco, 2023).

The literature underscores the importance of universities in promoting entrepreneurship as a means of fostering socioeconomic development (Pereira & Franco, 2023; Morawska-Jancelewicz, 2021). Thus, higher education institutions serve as critical platforms for nurturing future entrepreneurs and innovators through enterprise education programs (Kabongo & Okpara, 2010; Ndedi, 2013). Scholars argue for the unique role of universities in cultivating entrepreneurial mindsets and skills among students (Aga, 2023; Pacheco & Franco, 2023).

However, the effectiveness of such programs is sometimes contested, highlighting the need for more systematic research and assessment (Fayolle, 2013). Scholars and practitioners play a crucial role in informing educational policies and practices related to entrepreneurship education (Vankov et al., 2022).

3.1.2. Entrepreneurship education's pedagogical approaches :

Researchers argue that theoretical education, practical education, and the cultivation of an entrepreneurial atmosphere are all essential components of the entrepreneurship education teaching system (Wang Wei, 2007). The literature provides various pedagogical approaches or instructional techniques grounded in different perspectives on entrepreneurship education. However, there is a consensus that entrepreneurship education is often divided into three pedagogical approaches: educating about entrepreneurship, educating in entrepreneurship, and educating for entrepreneurship (Klapper & Farber, 2016).

Education about entrepreneurship primarily aims to foster an understanding of entrepreneurship, its frameworks, and the roles entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship play in societal and economic development (Klapper & Farber, 2016). These interventions often rely on the assumption that students passively acquire knowledge from instructors (Krueger, 2000; Liñán & Chen, 2009), labeled as supply-side teaching methods by Bechar & Gregoire (2005). Such methods typically involve traditional lectures, prescribed readings, and theoretical exploration of business startup concepts within university contexts (Klapper & Farber, 2016).

However, these approaches may slightly diminish students' sense of psychological distance, as they primarily provide explicit content knowledge without a procedural understanding of entrepreneurship (Leatherbee et al., 2020). Consequently, while students gain insight into entrepreneurial concepts, they lack firsthand entrepreneurial experiences needed to translate theoretical knowledge into actionable entrepreneurial endeavors (Leatherbee et al., 2020). Traditional lecture-based approaches have been supplemented and, in many cases, replaced by more interactive and experiential learning methods (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008).

Supply-side methods often emphasize the importance of social networks without offering guidance on how to establish them (Debarliev et al., 2020), resulting in a limited diminishment of perceived psychological distance.

On the other hand, demand-side teaching methods focus on experiential learning within the classroom, constituting educating in entrepreneurship (Bechard & Gregoire, 2005). These methods typically involve teacher-centered activities centered on secondary information and use market representations to address unmet needs and engage in problem-solving exercises (Hägg & Kurczewska, 2019).

Evaluation of demand-side methods suggests they primarily enhance students' procedural knowledge and skills related to venture creation processes (Neck & Corbett, 2018) (Nabi et al., 2017). However, they may not provide students with real-life entrepreneurial experiences necessary for acquiring tacit knowledge and may thus have a limited impact on turning environmental mindset into entrepreneurial actions (Neck & Corbett, 2018). Despite this, demand-side methods are expected to have a greater moderating effect compared to supply-side methods (Neck & Corbett, 2018).

Finally, competency-based teaching methods, which predominantly focus on problem-solving and higher-order learning, aim to educate for entrepreneurship (Klapper & Farber, 2016). Also known as venture creation programs (Alsos et al., 2023), these methods prioritize students' experiences and reflective understanding, with students assuming the role of entrepreneurs while engaging in real market problem-solving (Ratten & Jones, 2021; Hägg, 2021).

In this approach, students actively participate in constructing knowledge as they navigate through entrepreneurial challenges, guided by a collection of tools, techniques, and coaching (Alsos et al., 2023). Competency teaching methods facilitate the acquisition of procedural knowledge crucial for entrepreneurial activities, promote reflective experiential learning, and encourage social interaction both within and beyond the university environment (Alsos et al., 2023). This personalized and immersive learning environment helps diminish the perceived psychological distance and enhances students' readiness for entrepreneurial endeavors, making their learning more readily applicable to real-world situations (Alsos et al., 2023; Nabi et al., 2017).

Beyond higher education institutions, the academic community advocates for the importance of creating supportive environments for entrepreneurial activity (Belitski & Heron, 2017; Spigel, 2018) (Malecki, 2018). This underscores the significant effort and financial investment made by various stakeholders worldwide in supporting entrepreneurship education programs (Duval-Couetil, 2013).

on the other hand, scholars emphasize the importance of educators in EE. Liguori (2024) argues that entrepreneurship educators must prioritize teaching students how to learn over what to learn, stating that "Content is a commodity, this statement is true today and will likely be even more true in 10 years, meaning it is increasingly clear that how we teach is as, if not more, important than what we teach." this involves guiding them to distill wisdom from abundant information and fostering an environment of exploration and experimentation. Drawing parallels from entrepreneurship education to Mardi Gras, educators must promote structured yet agile learning experiences, engagement, action, and reflection (Winkler, 2024). Ultimately,

educators are responsible for cultivating a culture of active participation and continuous learning in the classroom (Winkler, 2024).

In this context, the supply of qualified and effective educators has been a neglected aspect in discussions surrounding entrepreneurship education (Byrne et al., 2014; Loi et al., 2016; Martin et al., 2013; Naia et al., 2014; Neck & Corbett, 2018; Samwel Mwasalwiba, 2010; Wang et al., 2014). In 2003, a Task Force established by the Entrepreneurship Division of the Academy of Management (AOM SIG), consisted of leading professors and doctoral directors, identified an increasing demand for faculty in entrepreneurship. They conducted surveys and made several recommendations to improve doctoral education in entrepreneurship (Brush, 2003).

Furthermore, the supply and training of doctoral students in entrepreneurship education have also emerged as significant topics of concern in recent years (Brush, 2003; Dunn et al., 2016; Milkman & McCoy, 2014; Schnader et al., 2016; Urbano et al., 2008). Changes in higher education have prompted discussions about teaching quality and the preparation of future professors (Golde, 2005; McAlpine & Norton, 2006). Concerns have also been raised about the effectiveness of business education and the focus on research excellence over teaching excellence (Ghoshal, 2005; Lewicki & Bailey, 2009; Mintzberg & Gosling, 2002; Pfeffer & Fong, 2002). These concerns extend to the design of doctoral programs, highlighting inconsistencies in teaching competency development and instructional training for teacher preparation (Marx et al., 2016).

Doctoral education is viewed as a socialization process, where students acquire the knowledge, skills, and characteristics associated with their profession (Tierney & Rhoads, 1994; Weidman et al., 2001). This process involves moving from a beginner to a higher level of professional maturity and entails both cognitive and affective dimensions (Brim & Wheeler, 1967; Weidman et al., 2001). However, research on educator development in doctoral programs has been limited, focusing primarily on the perspective of doctoral directors and lacking consideration of students' experiences (Lewicki & Bailey, 2009; Marx et al., 2016). There is a recognized need to engage students in a socialization process that encompasses cognitive and affective dimensions (Weidman et al., 2001).

On another hand, with the recent advancement in technology, Digital Entrepreneurship Education (DEE) appears. DEE prepares students for the dynamic digital landscape, promoting adaptability and readiness for transformation (Kickul et al., 2018). Technological advancements in this form of education include the innovative use of robots, and Artificial Intelligence to enhance the learning experience (Ratten & Jones, 2021). Yet, there is a lack of studies on the use of AI in business education, including entrepreneurship education (Vecchiarini & Somià, 2023). Additionally, the debate over its use has been especially controversial in academia (García-Peñalvo, 2023).

3.2. Entrepreneurial Intention :

Many scholars have defined Entrepreneurial Intention over the years. The first definition to exist of (EI) was by (Bird, 1988), he describes it as a psychological state that guides an entrepreneur's focus, energy, and actions toward a particular goal. Krueger (1993) in contrast, defined EI as a “ commitment to start a new business”, bringing a more action-oriented perspective to the concept. Similarly, Liñán (2004) argued that EI represents “the effort that the person will make to carry out that entrepreneurial behavior”. Expanding on

these definitions, Qian Yonghong (2007), and Ye Yinghua (2009) see it as the subjective attitude of potential entrepreneurs toward engaging in entrepreneurial activities, framing it as a planned and deliberate behavior that represents a commitment to starting a business.

In essence, an individual's entrepreneurial intention is one of the most reliable indicators of their entrepreneurial behavior. EI is often used by scholars to describe the extent of entrepreneurial traits, attitudes, and abilities (Qian Yonghong, 2007, Ye Yinghua, 2009). According to Mudalige (2022), intention becomes the key factor in explaining and understanding behavior in any context. In addition, Adeel et al. (2023) recognize EI as an antecedent of entrepreneurial behavior. Building on these foundational definitions, researchers have developed several theoretical frameworks to better understand entrepreneurial intention.

Aldrich and Zimmer (1986, p. 3) suggested that entrepreneurial activity “can be conceptualized as a function of opportunity structures and motivated entrepreneurs with access to resources”. linking EI to external conditions and resources essential for entrepreneurial success. While the origins of entrepreneurial intention are essential (Yifan et al., 2023), the factors that influence it are also vital. Some scholars argue that primary determinants include innovativeness, market demand, feasibility, profit model, and teamwork (Dawoud A. et al., 2022). Yet within the Chinese context, scholars emphasize factors such as achievement motivation, risk-taking, autonomy, entrepreneurial feedback (individual trait level), resource acquisition, and future employment (individual resource level), thereby categorizing them into two levels (Qian Y., 2007).

Although many scholars agree that individual traits are determinants of entrepreneurial intention, they differ on the factors composing these traits. Adeel et al. (2023) and, Liñán (2004) both argue that EI is shaped by factors like prior knowledge, entrepreneurial alertness, opportunity recognition, and entrepreneurial motivation. Prior knowledge encompasses an individual's accumulated knowledge and experiences (work and non-work experiences), including work and education, that relate to entrepreneurial capabilities (Ardichvili and Cardozo, 2000). Entrepreneurial alertness, on the other hand, refers to the “ability to notice without search opportunities that have hitherto been overlooked” (Kirzner, 1979, p. 48), highlighting the importance of being able to recognize opportunities in an ever-changing environment.

To systematically study and predict EI, scholars often turn to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), a model proposed by (Ajzen, 1991) that is widely used in the literature to understand behavioral intentions. TPB posits that an individual's behavioral intention is influenced by three factors: Behavioral attitude, Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC), and Perceived Social Norms (PSN).

In this context, Attitude toward the behavior denotes the extent to which an individual has a positive or negative personal assessment of becoming an entrepreneur, with studies showing that more positive attitudes lead to higher entrepreneurial intentions (Mudalige, 2022; Fang, 2017). Perceived behavioral control (PBC), or perceived feasibility (PF), refers to an individual's perception of their capability to engage in entrepreneurial activities, thus determining the feasibility of firm creation from their perspective (Adeel et al., 2023; Mudalige, 2022). Perceived social norms (PSN) or Subjective Norms (SN) represent the social pressures an individual perceives in either pursuing or avoiding entrepreneurial behavior (Mudalige, 2022). Therefore, those three factors are key factors determining entrepreneurial intention.

In a study by Tan et al. (2015), EE was found to significantly enhance college students' entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The study concluded that these improvements collectively impact students' intention to pursue entrepreneurship, primarily through increased entrepreneurial knowledge, which strengthens their perceived behavioral control. Hassan et al., (2022), similarly concluded that EE positively influences the entrepreneurial intention of university students in India, both directly and indirectly, through increased self-efficacy, which serves as a proxy for perceived behavioral control.

Based on what is discussed in the literature above, we formulate the following hypothesis:

- H1:** The constructs of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) influence directly Entrepreneurial Intention.
- H2:** Opportunity recognition influence directly Entrepreneurial Intention.
- H3:** Prior knowledge, Entrepreneurial alertness, and Entrepreneurial Motivation influence indirectly Entrepreneurial Intention.
- H4:** Entrepreneurship education influences, directly and indirectly, entrepreneurial intention.

3.2. Entrepreneurship education & Entrepreneurial intention :

As aforementioned, entrepreneurship is primarily taught through education programs, either formal or informal, delivered as business curricula (European Commission, 2017; UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2012) (Liu, 2021; Valerio et al., 2014). Those programs focus on developing various skills (cognitive and non-cognitive), beliefs, or intentions. In addition to the variety of their focus, entrepreneurship education programs were shown to deliver mixed results.

Generally, the existing studies in the literature show the positive effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention. Bjorvatn et al., (2020) study, is backing Oosterbeek et al., (2010) proposal exploring additional program variations to gain a deeper insight into its potential. where television replaced in-person teaching. they noted a favorable impact on intention in a sample of 2132 students. However, despite this positive influence, the authors raised doubts about the overall efficacy of their intervention, as it failed to result in increased business ownership. They recommended a more comprehensive investigation of different program adaptations to enhance comprehension of its potential. Also, Athayde's (2009) study reported a positive impact on intention, skills, and beliefs as well. The author studied 276 secondary school students in the United Kingdom (UK) in a longitudinal randomized control trial.

Some research findings show inconsistencies and non-significant effects. A study conducted in Tanzania showed no significant changes in intention but a favorable one in skills (Krause et al., 2016). In Germany, Grewe & Brahm (2020) in their study, found significant improvements in cognitive skills but null results in non-cognitive ones. In urban Jordan, Aljaouni et al., (2020) examined the impact of their educational program on a sample of 1630 students and found a decrease in entrepreneurial intention alongside an increase in entrepreneurial awareness, with no impact on beliefs. Also, a study conducted by Solesvik (2013) of selected Ukrainian university students found that exposing students to enterprise education had no statistically significant impact on their subjective norms.

EE results can be positive, neutral, or even negative. In different settings, the same entrepreneurship program can deliver different results, as programs based on the Junior Achievement Young Enterprise mini-company program did in the Netherlands (Oosterbeek et al., 2010), Portugal (Paço & Palinhas, 2011), Sweden (Elert et al., 2015), and the UK (Athayde, 2012).

Although the different countries of implementation may raise questions about whether culture determined the different results, the study designs offered some similarities to suggest comparison is possible. It has to be noted that Elert et al., (2015) accessed census data, following up with program graduates up to 16 years post-graduation and matching them with a similar group that did not undertake the program. Despite those positive aspects of the studies, they still suffered from the already identified limitations that all of them utilized formal education settings and neither of them grounded their methodology in a suitable theory.

4. DISCUSSION

In recent years, as the theory and practice of entrepreneurship education (EE) have been extensively studied, many scholars have come to believe that this education plays a significant role in enhancing college students' entrepreneurial intention (EI), especially when viewed through the lens of Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). This model suggests that EE plays a key role in shaping entrepreneurial attitudes, enhancing perceived behavioral control, and promoting opportunity recognition, all of which are fundamental to forming a strong entrepreneurial intention (Luthje et al., 2002). University graduates who have participated in entrepreneurship courses are more inclined to pursue entrepreneurial careers and engage in patentable innovations (Luthje et al., 2002). Mudalige (2022) further asserts that "Entrepreneurial conduct and entrepreneurial tendency are both influenced by entrepreneurship education". Ripollés & Blesa (2023) assert that entrepreneurship education is essential in forming an individual's entrepreneurial behavior.

A research conducted by Duan Limin et al. (2012) focused on understanding the factors influencing the EI of college students in China. They developed a model tailored to China's unique national conditions. Their findings highlighted EE's role in shaping students' entrepreneurial intention through the TPB components. Similarly, Saeed et al., (2015) found that a strong entrepreneurial education infrastructure and university support for entrepreneurship boosted students' entrepreneurial self-efficacy and intention. Other studies by Izquierdo & Buelens (2011), Lüthje et al. (2002), Peterman et al. (2003), and Souitaris et al. (2007) discovered that entrepreneurial education plays a significant role in shaping students' entrepreneurial intention.

According to Farashah (2013), EE shifts people's attitudes toward entrepreneurship by reducing their fear of failure and heightening their ability to recognize opportunities. This positive shift in behavioral attitude increases the perceived attractiveness of entrepreneurship as a career path, addressing the TPB component of attitude. EE also promotes a positive social image of entrepreneurship, enhancing the subjective norms component by normalizing entrepreneurship in the social environment. Additionally, EE also boosts self-efficacy by equipping individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills to start a business, directly impacting perceived behavioral control (Farashah, 2013). University-based EE programs—including lectures, courses, and career guidance—help shape students' entrepreneurial experiences, which in turn influences their awareness and motivation for entrepreneurship (Dou et al., 2019).

Researchers in entrepreneurship education frequently apply the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to model entrepreneurial intent as a precursor to new venture creation (Krueger, 2000; Schlegel et al., 2014). An entrepreneurship educator can influence the three constructs of TPB by enhancing students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship (Behavioral Attitude), their perception of its acceptance within their social environment (Subjective Norms), and their sense of the ease of engaging in entrepreneurial activities (Perceived Behavioral Control or Perceived Feasibility) (Krueger et al., 2000; Schlegel et al., 2014).

In a study by Tan et al. (2015), EE was found to significantly enhance college students' entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The study concluded that these improvements in knowledge, ability, and attitude collectively impact students' intention to pursue entrepreneurship, primarily through the pathway of increased entrepreneurial knowledge. Hassan et al., (2022) similarly concluded that EE positively influences the entrepreneurial intention of university students in India, both directly and indirectly through increased self-efficacy, which serves as a proxy for perceived behavioral control.

Additionally, Adeel et al., (2023) argue that EE enhances the relationships between individual traits such as prior knowledge, entrepreneurial alertness, opportunity recognition, entrepreneurial motivation, and entrepreneurial intention. Their findings supported hypotheses indicating the positive impacts of prior knowledge on opportunity recognition and entrepreneurial alertness. Entrepreneurial alertness was shown to enhance both opportunity recognition and entrepreneurial motivation, which in turn positively influence entrepreneurial intention.

Among the various determinants of EI, opportunity recognition emerges as particularly influential and is a primary outcome of EE's impact. Hassan et al., 2020 studied this impact by surveying 334 Indian students with business and management backgrounds, concluding that opportunity recognition positively affects students' entrepreneurial intention. Ryu et al. (2020) analyzed data from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitoring (GEM) database across 15 countries, finding that opportunity recognition consistently influences EI across diverse cultural contexts. Similarly, Botha & Taljaard (2019), and Wannamakok et al. (2020) also found a strong positive relationship between opportunity recognition and entrepreneurial intention in their studies, underscoring the critical role that recognizing viable business opportunities plays in entrepreneurial decision-making (Liñán, 2007).

To sum up what has been stated, we can say that EE contributes to shaping EI by positively impacting the components of the TPB: attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and subjective norms (Dou et al., 2019; Saeed et al., 2015; Farashah, 2013; Lüthje et al., 2002, Schlaegel et al., 2014). Through effectively cultivating the traits and motivations critical for developing a strong entrepreneurial intention (Adeel et al., 2023; Dou et al., 2019; Farashah, 2013).

Figure 1: Effect of entrepreneurship education on the determinants of entrepreneurial intention

Source: own elaboration

This model is based on Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior while incorporating the specific impact of entrepreneurship education on the determinants of entrepreneurial intention.

5. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the important role of entrepreneurship education in shaping the determinants of entrepreneurial intention among higher education students. By reviewing recent literature, we found that entrepreneurship education positively influences key factors. However, the impact varies across different educational contexts and methodologies. The findings support the value of entrepreneurship education in fostering an entrepreneurial mindset. Overall, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of how educational programs can effectively promote entrepreneurship among students, emphasizing the importance of continued innovation and assessment in entrepreneurship education.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS:

This study of the impact of entrepreneurship education on the determinants of entrepreneurial behavior among higher education students is subject to several limitations. First, the reliance on only studies in the English language may introduce selection bias, as relevant studies in other languages might have been excluded. Additionally, the heterogeneity of the included studies, in terms of varying educational contexts, methodologies, and definitions of entrepreneurial intention, may limit the generalizability of the conclusions drawn. Lastly, the study's method lacks quantitative rigor. In future research, we plan to test these results in an empirical study.

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